

CORRECTIVE FEEDBACK IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract:

Achieving production with the fewest faults made by learners in the output is the main goal of English Language Teaching. Constructive feedback is essential to achieving this goal because it is effective in enhancing language learners' proficiency. One of the most beneficial educational interventions in language instruction is giving feedback. The omnipresent role of feedback and related instructional tactics in language courses are highlighted in this essay. The research aims to investigate feedback mechanisms that differ in various circumstances and compare them to the corpus of literature on language training.

Key words: feedback, error correction, language skills development, correction mechanisms, role of comments.

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At a non-linguistic university, teaching foreign languages aims to equip students with the knowledge and skills required for both written and oral communication. These include professional and general conversation, as well as the ability to extract essential information from texts in foreign languages and present it in the form of annotations and abstracts.

It is crucial to continuously assess the student's advancement and accomplishments while also motivating them to take little "victories" every day. Right from the start of the learning task, the instructor should assist the students in creating accurate and impartial standards by which to judge their performance. Without a doubt, the student needs to gain an understanding of the language's intricate structure and the vast amount of knowledge needed to speak it fluently. The student must comprehend why learning a foreign language requires so much work and be appropriately guided through each learning phase. The student will then be both more realistic and upbeat about his meager progress.

Avoiding communicative errors—those that impede comprehension and, consequently, communication—is the primary objective. While there is still work to be done on speech correctness, it should be kept in mind that sometimes we expect learners to produce far more flawless utterances than they would in their native tongue. It is appropriate to discuss here the requirements related to different aspects of speech that stem from the training goal of giving the trainees the ability to use a foreign language practically. Leontiev proposed such an optimal set of requirements. He suggests that the degree of "intelligibility" of speech—that is, its ability to be understood by a speaker of the language as a native speaker—be considered as one of these requirements. This primarily relates to the pronunciation of the student.

Leontief cites the linguistic fact that phonemes and sound-types do not coincide in language as support for this requirement for phonetics. Regarding vocabulary, Leontief

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vehemently disputes the idea that learning is a process of memorization. Instead, he suggests using a mechanism of memory known as imprinting, which takes place when a learner generates a tension known as a "speech need" and is then reinforced by the satisfaction of that need. This process best matches the circumstances of real-world communication. When reading and listening, new vocabulary is best acquired when a word or expression is unfamiliar and demands clarification of understanding. A pronunciation error is regarded as a departure from the standard for literary pronunciation. Literary pronunciation is defined as the norm in which a given language group crystallizes one pronunciation of a word /phoneme/ or type of intonation as the proper variant while permitting the coexistence of other variants of equally correct, but less common pronunciation when there is shared characteristics in the perception and reproduction of words, phonemes, and intonation.

As a result, infractions and errors are recognized as two different categories of departure from the norm. Pronunciation errors are examples of deviations from the norm that maintain the semantic function of speech, don't affect mutual understanding, and don't destroy the shared characteristics of perception of the statement. A dramatic departure from the intonation and phoneme commonality that characterize the literary pronunciation norm of a given language, along with the introduction of foreign phonetic phenomena, are regarded as a distortion of the norm because they undermine the semantic function of speech, the standardized nature of perception of the statement, and the guarantee of mutual understanding.

Errors of distortion of the norm are what define the learner. These are the ones that need to be fixed initially. Any error made should be recognized by the trainees in terms of its semantic ramifications, i.e., the degree to which it impedes accurate speech comprehension. Errors can only be handled correctly if one acknowledges the necessity of intentionally analyzing them. To overcome a mistake, learners—especially adults—must consciously analyze their own mistakes.

Grammar mistakes are exposed when translating a document between the current and final controls. These mistakes stem from inadequate or nonexistent skill development. One of the most prevalent issues is students' incapacity to use dictionaries correctly. Many times, students believe that if they are permitted to use a dictionary during a written exam, there won't be any issues with translation. However, they do happen. Rather than providing the precise definition of a word, some students frequently provide an approximation and believe they grasp the general meaning. Others look up every word in the dictionary; they write down every word they are unsure of first, and then they translate it. Semantic mistakes result when a word appears out of context and in isolation. Many mistakes are caused by misidentifying parts of speech or by trying to look up a verb's form in a dictionary instead of its infinitive. As a result, careful consideration should be given to the verb tenses and their formation, as well as the word-forming components of parts of speech and the sequence in which English word combinations are constructed. The latter, which includes the active and passive voice, should be studied in groups (Indefinite, Continuous, Perfect). This idea helps dispel the notion of a "chaotic scattering" of verb forms, guarantee form memorization, and improve understanding of the verb system. It should be simple for the student to identify and discern between things like Present Continuous and Past Perfect. As a result, it is advised to start studying tenses by examining and evaluating the summary table of English verb tenses, taking note of how the three verb tenses are used differently.

We distinguished six different types of feedback regarded as effective by EFL teachers.

1. The act of providing of the correct form explicitly is referred to as explicit correction. The teacher makes it obvious that the student's statement was inaccurate as they offer the proper form (e.g., "Oh, you mean," "You should say").

2. In a recast, the teacher reformulates all or a portion of a student's statement, taking out the mistake. Reformulations like "paraphrase," "repetition with change," and "repetition with change and emphasis" are referred to here. In general, recasts are implicit because they don't begin with expressions like "You mean," "Use this word," or "You should say." But some recasts stand out more than others because they may concentrate on a single word, while others integrate the lexical or grammatical change into a longer discourse. Translations made in response to a student using the L1 are also included in recasts.

3. As stated by Spada (1995, p. 25), requests for clarification serve as a cue to students that their statements are either poorly formed or that the teacher misunderstood them and that they need to be repeated or rephrased. This kind of feedback can address issues with accuracy, comprehensibility, or both. Only in cases where these actions come after a student error have, we coded feedback as requests for clarification. A "Pardon me?" request is an example of a clarification request. The mistake could also be repeated, as in "What do you mean by X?"

4. Metalinguistic feedback does not specifically state the proper form; instead, it offers questions, remarks, or details regarding how well-formed the student's speech was. Metalinguistic remarks (e.g., "Can you find your error?" "No, not X,") typically suggest that there is a mistake somewhere. When a lexical error occurs, metalinguistic information typically offers a word definition or some grammatical metalanguage indicating the type of error (e.g., "It's masculine"). Metalinguistic questions, such as "Is it feminine?" aim to elicit information from the student while also pointing out the nature of the error.

5. The term "elicitation" describes one or more of the three methods teachers employ to ask students to directly provide the right form. In order to help students "fill in the blank," as it were, teachers first elicit completion of their own utterance by purposefully pausing (e.g., "This is..."). Moves like "elicit completion" could be accompanied by a metalinguistic statement like "No, not that." "It's a..." or by making the same mistake twice. Second, educators ask questions (such as "How do we say X in English?") to elicit the proper forms. Yes/no questions are not allowed in these types of inquiries. A query like "Do we say that in English?" is not an elicitation question; rather, it is metalinguistic feedback. Third, educators will sometimes ask pupils to rephrase what they have said.

6. The term "repetition" signifies the teacher repeating the student's incorrect statement once. Most of the time, instructors change their tone to draw attention to the mistake.

With the development of the communicative approach to teaching foreign languages, learners' errors began to be considered as an integral part of the educational process. Mistakes serve as a signal to pay attention to certain topics and close gaps in knowledge. In addition, they help learners to track their progress in teaching foreign language. Corrective feedback emerged as a natural reaction to learners' erroneous statements. Thus, corrective feedback is a response to written or oral products that contain an error. However, it is obviously only possible to provide feedback in this manner as part of a negotiated sequence in L2 classrooms where students have already reached a sufficient proficiency level. The four feedback types that function to actively involve students in the negotiation of form continue to be nonthreatening and possibly helpful if this requirement is satisfied. Therefore, it goes without saying that mistakes made when teaching a foreign language should be corrected:

permanently, during the beginning stages and initial activation of the teaching material; selectively, during the speech practice process, when the error causes a communication

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